

Multi-scale modeling of a wind turbine wake in complex terrain

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Abstract. Comparing numerical simulations of wind turbine wakes in neutral atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) flow over complex terrains with full-scale experiments is not always straightforward. Pure neutral ABL conditions are rarely found in the atmosphere as the characteristics of the ABL change during the diurnal cycle. This study presents some insights into how a single wind turbine (WT) and its wake behave under near-neutral ABL conditions in complex terrain. The Perdigão Valley in Portugal was chosen as the test case as it is an excellent case study of three-dimensional flow in complex terrain to validate numerical simulations of WT wake with experimental data due to the availability of extensively deployed remote sensing equipment (e.g., German Aerospace Center (DLR) and Technical University of Denmark (DTU) multi-Doppler lidars). The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) [1] model is utilized in large-eddy simulation (LES) mode in order to simulate the period of interest with a multi-scale modeling approach. Five nested domains, with the finest domain having a spatial resolution of 5 m, are used to dynamically downscale mesoscale flow features to microscale. A generalized actuator line (GAL) WT parameterization is used to model the wind turbine-flow interaction. WRF-LES-GAL (hereinafter referred to as WLG) results compare quite well with the experimental data obtained from lidars and meteorological mast, with minor biases between the simulated and observed data. Due to insufficient buoyancy generation from the WRF-LES model, the simulated track wake was found to have lower vertical deflection compared to the lidar data; hence, no recirculation zone is observed in the valley. Overall, the WLG model is able to reproduce the wake characteristics observed on the first ridge top into the valley, as well as the power and thrust generation, and can be used for further analysis of other stability conditions.

1. Introduction

Complex terrains with high wind resources are interesting sites for wind farms, as they are far from the urban environment and, therefore, exempt from strict regulations regarding wind turbine installation on flat terrains close to residential areas [2]. Also, these terrains are better suited for extracting maximum kinetic energy from the wind because the flow in mountainous areas (e.g., at ridges) tends to accelerate, enabling wind turbines to generate more power, especially when the winds are perpendicular to mountain ranges [3]. On top of a hill and downstream of the ridge, there are regions with higher average wind speeds, which can be attributed to the higher power output of a wind turbine installed in these regions. However,

Table 1: Mean freestream wind speed, \bar{U} , friction velocity, u_* , surface kinematic heat flux, $(\overline{w'\theta'})_s$, Obukhov length, L , and non-dimensional Froude number, F_L , obtained from different met masts.

Met mast	Experimental					Numerical				
	\bar{U} [m s ⁻¹]	u_* [m s ⁻¹]	$(\overline{w'\theta'})_s$ [K m s ⁻¹]	L [m]	F_L [-]	\bar{U} [m s ⁻¹]	u_* [m s ⁻¹]	$(\overline{w'\theta'})_s$ [K m s ⁻¹]	L [m]	F_L [-]
TSE04	7.3	0.33	0.009	-291.3	∞	9.9	0.45	0.006	-1027.6	1.4
TSE09	2.8	0.41	-0.009	531.5	-	4.8	0.17	-0.006	59.0	-
TSE13	6.4	0.58	0.010	-1411.8	0.7	11.1	0.53	-0.002	6244.4	2.1

Note. \bar{U} and F_L are calculated at 100 m, while u_* , $(\overline{w'\theta'})_s$ and L are calculated at 10 m. Experimental values are calculated from 20 Hz experimental data, while numerical values are calculated from high-frequency simulation data resampled at 20 Hz.

steep topography can also lead to high flow slope angles and high turbulence regions (even flow recirculation areas) [4, 5, 6], which may cause an increase in wind turbine loading and power variability if the wind turbine location is not carefully decided. The topology of the flow in these regions is affected not only by the topography but also by the stability conditions of the atmosphere [4]. As a result of the dynamic behavior of the ABL during the diurnal cycle, wind turbine performance and wake propagation are affected by the change in atmospheric stability, as the terrain-induced flow and wind turbine wake interact dynamically.

Gaining insight into the wind turbine wake characteristics induced by flow over complex terrains is essential to better assess terrain-wake interaction and maximize the wind energy harvesting from a well-located wind turbine, while keeping the loading in acceptable levels. Large changes in topography causes flow separation and recirculation zones downhill of steep terrain [7], making it difficult to model atmospheric flows over complex terrain. High turbulence levels, gustiness, and sudden changes in wind speed and wind direction found in these regions mean a serious challenge to be reproduced numerically with the accuracy required by wind energy applications [8].

The atmosphere is a dynamic system involving a wide range of scales. Therefore, proper modeling of the turbulent flow driving wind turbine dynamics requires accurate reproduction from large atmospheric scales down to scales of the order of the blade boundary layer width. Numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, such as the WRF model, have the advantage of not only solving atmospheric multi-physics through dynamic downscaling from mesoscale to microscale but also the capability to incorporate real topography; therefore, they are often favored by many modelers [9, 10].

The aim of this study is to validate the WLG model against field measurements by investigating the ability of the WLG model to capture a single wake of a wind turbine under near-neutral atmospheric conditions, which is rarely observed in complex terrain. This study also analyzes the aerodynamic performance of a wind turbine at the Perdigão site. The near-neutral ABL conditions examined herein are chosen as a reference case for further analysis of other stability conditions. Special attention is paid to the understanding of turbulence characteristics, wake propagation, characterization of unstable aerodynamic loads of the wind turbine, and power estimation for near-neutral ABL conditions. The predicted microscale flow structures and wake behavior of the wind turbine are validated by directly comparing the WLG model results with high-frequency experimental data from two met masts on the ridges and one met mast in the valley, as well as remote sensing data from DLR and DTU.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the methodology, including a brief description of the Perdigão field campaign and some key points on mesoscale-microscale modeling, and a wind turbine parameterization using the WLG model [11]. In Section 3, the flow turbulence characteristics obtained from the WLG model are compared with experimental

Table 2: Domain dimensions and model configuration parameters.

Domain	$N_x \times N_y \times N_z$	$\Delta x = \Delta y$ [m]	Δz [m]	Δt [s]	Turb. model	CPM	Spin-up [min]
d01	$141 \times 141 \times 41$	5000	~ 80	30	Shin-Hong	No	600
d02	$151 \times 181 \times 61$	1000	~ 50	6	Shin-Hong	No	600
d03	$241 \times 241 \times 81$	125	~ 30	0.6	1.5-order TKE	Yes	420
d04	$271 \times 271 \times 121$	25	~ 15	0.06	1.5-order TKE	Yes	60
d05	$501 \times 501 \times 201$	5	~ 5	0.0075	1.5-order TKE	Yes	10

Note. N_x, N_y and N_z stand for the number of grid points whereas $\Delta x, \Delta y$ and Δz represent the spatial grid resolutions in the x, y and z directions, respectively. Note that Δz is set close to the values given in the table, because of WRF's terrain-following eta coordinate system in the vertical direction. Δt is the computational time-step size. CPM denotes the Cell Perturbation Method [14].

data obtained at three 100 m height met masts and from the DLR and DTU lidar scans across vertical planes. Simulated one-hour time series of wind turbine power output and thrust are also presented. Conclusions are drawn in the final section (Section 4).

2. Methodology

2.1. The Perdigão field campaign and selection of the test case

As a part of the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) validation experiment, funded by the European Union [12], an intensive operation period (IOP) campaign took place in 2017, from May 1th to June 15th, during the Perdigão field experiment in Portugal [3]. A large group of scientists, engineers and research organizations from all around the world, worked in collaboration to explore the microscale flow over a complex terrain region in Perdigão Valley, which consists of two parallel mountain ridges at about 460 m above sea level and extends over 2 km distance [13]. The prevailing wind direction was perpendicular to the orientation of the ridges in general (southwesterly winds) [3].

In the present work, the atmospheric flow over Perdigão Valley is modeled for one hour period when actual atmospheric conditions at the site were found to be near-neutral (measurement period on 09/05/2017 between 22:00-23:00 UTC). In order to determine the state of the ABL, several parameters such as the Obukhov length, L , can be estimated. L is the ratio between buoyant and mechanical effects on the atmospheric turbulence, given as

$$L = \frac{-u_*^3 \bar{\theta}}{\kappa g (\overline{w'\theta'})_s}, \quad (1)$$

where $u_* = (\overline{u'w'^2} + \overline{v'w'^2})^{0.25}$ is the friction velocity, $\bar{\theta}$ is the mean potential temperature, $\kappa = 0.41$ is the von Kármán constant, $g = 9.81 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ is the gravitational acceleration, w is the vertical velocity and $\overline{w'\theta'}$ is the surface kinematic heat flux. The prime and overbar denote the fluctuation and time-average, respectively.

In complex terrain, non-dimensional Froude number, F_L , can also be used to determine the atmospheric stability in areas where hills or mountainous regions occupy a significant portion of the ABL [4]. It is defined as

$$F_L = \frac{U}{NL_h}, \quad (2)$$

with U being the characteristic velocity in the ABL, $N = \sqrt{\frac{g}{\bar{\theta}} \frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial z}}$ is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, that is the frequency of an air particle displaced vertically within a statically stable environment, with $\partial \bar{\theta} / \partial z$ being the potential temperature gradient, z denotes the height and L_h is the characteristic downwind length of the hill (e.g., mountain ridge width). In this work, $\partial \bar{\theta} / \partial z$

Figure 1: Stationary curves of power, P (a), thrust, T (b), power coefficient, C_P (c) and thrust coefficient, C_T (d), versus wind speed, V of the generic Vestas V80 2MW [18] and Enercon E-82 2MW [19] wind turbines.

is calculated from the temperature gradient between 100 and 10 m, while other values are calculated at 100 m, with $L_h = 586.5$ m at the southwest (SW) ridge and $L_h = 530.0$ m at the northeast (NE) ridge, respectively [10, 15].

For $F_L \gg 1$, the wind flow is supercritical, meaning that boundary layer separation may occur in the lee side of the mountain due to strong winds. $F_L \ll 1$ corresponds to subcritical flow and the ABL is statically very stable and mountain waves may form [16]. In the case of $F_L \sim \infty$, the state of the ABL can be classified as either convective or neutral and recirculation regions may form [10]. Measured and simulated stability parameters obtained from different met masts at Perdigão test site are given in Table 1. The state of the ABL is classified as neutral if $|L| \geq 500$, unstable if $-500 < L < 0$ and stable when $0 < L < 500$ [17]. According to the stability parameters given in Table 1, the period of interest considered in this work can be classified as near-neutral based on the stability parameters obtained from TSE04 mast because the prevailing wind direction at hub height is approximately 228° , and thus, other met masts stay in the wake of the first ridge during the period of interest (see Figure 2b). The large discrepancy between the experimental and numerical data is due to the overestimation of the mean wind speed over the ridges, and bias in the surface heat flux and friction velocity at the met mast locations.

2.2. Mesoscale-microscale modeling with WRF-LES

Time series of different flow variables at several locations at the Perdigão test site were collected from meteorological masts, lidars, sodars, radiosondes, microphones, a tethered lifting system (TLS), etc., installed by several research groups from different institutions [3]. A single Enercon E-82 2MW WT is located on the southwestern ridge (Figure 2a).

A rich variety of flow types such as buoyancy-driven anabatic (upslope) and katabatic (downslope) flows, valley flows driven by large temperature gradients along the valley and separated flows at the ridges that are caused by the interaction of topography with synoptic flow are observed at the test site. Due to the comprehensive deployment of experimental means, the Perdigão database offers a unique opportunity to investigate the wind turbine wake dynamics under various atmospheric stability conditions in complex terrain [3].

Sonic anemometers installed at different heights above ground level are utilized to acquire

Figure 2: WRF-LES-d05 domain showing the locations of wind turbine, DLR and DTU lidars, 100 m DTU met masts, wake and offset transects (a), and color map of 1-hour average horizontal wind speed at hub height, \bar{U} , corresponding to the period on 09/05/2017 between 22:00-23:00 UTC (b), where the wind turbine is represented by a black line and its wake is encircled by a pink ellipse.

20 Hz data from the three 100 m met masts (TSE04, TSE09 and TSE13 that are located on the SW ridge, in the valley and on the NE ridge, respectively (see Figure 2a). These high-frequency measurement data (NCAR/EOL Quality Controlled High-rate ISFS surface flux data, geographic coordinate, tilt corrected, version 1.1 [20]) are used as reference to validate the WRF-LES results in terms of horizontal wind speed, wind direction, spectra and cospectra of flow velocity components and cospectra of vertical momentum and heat flux, respectively.

Scanning Doppler lidar data from two lidars installed by DLR (DLR85 and DLR86, which are located in the valley and on the NE ridge, respectively, see Figure 2a) are also employed for comparison of experimental and numerical data presented in this work [21]. These lidars are of the Range Height Indicator (RHI) type and scan the flow velocity field along radial directions in a vertical plane containing the wind turbine tower, which allow the details of the WT wake and valley flow to be captured when the wind blows in the WT-lidar direction. The azimuth angle of DLR lidars in the horizontal plane is approximately constant; thus, the scanning trajectory is perpendicular to the wind turbine rotor. Likewise, DTU lidars have a constant azimuth angle but scan the offset transect. However, as the terrain has a similar topography along the nearly parallel transects (the actual distance between these transects is roughly 182.4 m on the first ridge and 129.6 m on the second ridge), DTU lidar scans can provide information about wind flow topology along the offset transect without being affected by the wind turbine wake. Note that, DLR85 and DLR86 lidar scans (sweeps) take about 53 s and 113 s, while a DTU multi-Doppler lidar completes a single sweep in about 24 s. Besides, the radial velocities measured by the lidars have been converted into horizontal velocities for comparison. Converting radial velocity to horizontal velocity leads to larger errors at higher elevation angles but smaller errors along the valley near the wind turbine where the lidar beam is nearly horizontal [10]. This transformation results in zero horizontal velocity at vertical positions along the lidar beam, perpendicular to the mean flow direction at the lidar location.

An online mesoscale-microscale coupling approach with five one-way nested domains provided by the WRF model is utilized. Mesoscale simulations are performed with two nested domains, with horizontal resolutions of $\Delta x = 5000$ m and 1000 m, using the Shin-Hong planetary boundary layer (PBL) scheme [22]. Three microscale domains, with horizontal resolutions of $\Delta x = 125$ m, 25 m and 5 m, are run in LES mode using a 1.5-order turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) sub-filter

Figure 3: Comparison of time series of instantaneous horizontal wind speed, U (first row), and wind direction, β (second row) at hub height and 100-10 m potential temperature gradient, $d\theta/dz$ (third row), obtained from TSE04 (first column), TSE09 (second column) and TSE13 (third column) met masts, and numerical results corresponding to WRF-LES-d05. Note that the numerical data were subsampled to 0.05 s intervals to match the experimental data. t (UTC) stands for Coordinated Universal Time in hours and minutes.

scale (SFS) turbulence scheme [23]. Vertical grid nesting is applied to all domains to allow for vertical grid refinement over nested domains by reducing the overall time required to run the model. Details of the computational domain are given in Table 2.

Temporal discretization is achieved by using a third-order Runge–Kutta scheme, with fifth-order horizontal and third-order vertical advection schemes. Physical parameterizations include the Eta (Ferrier) scheme for microphysics [24], the Noah land surface model [25], the Rapid Radiative Transfer Model for longwave radiation [26] and the Dudhia shortwave radiation model [27]. Revised MM5 surface layer scheme is used on all domains [28]. Shading effects on the surface heat flux are enabled by setting the *topo_shading* parameter to 1. The model top is placed at 150 hPa (about 13.5 km in altitude) to take into account radiation and cloud effects at the tropopause [29] and for the upper 5 km of the domain, a Rayleigh damping layer is used to dampen the spurious waves that could be reflected from the model top.

A high-resolution reanalysis dataset (e.g., European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF ERA5) [30]) for initial and lateral boundary conditions is used to provide the atmospheric forcing required on all domains. A synthetic turbulence generation algorithm, called the Cell Perturbation Method (CPM) [14], is applied to trigger the generation of realistic atmospheric turbulence on the LES domains. The Coordination of Information on the Environment (CORINE) Land Cover 2012 raster dataset with a spatial resolution of 100 m [31] is used to account for tall vegetation. These data are transformed into United States Geological Survey (USGS) land use types to obtain surface roughness lengths for WRF [32]. Besides, in order to resolve flow features in the valley surface, a high-resolution terrain data from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission with a spatial resolution of 30 m [33] is also used.

The spin-up of the nested domains is achieved by performing a set of restart model runs. This is necessary to obtain well-developed turbulent structures within the finest resolution domain, which contains the modeled wind turbine. Domains d01 and d02 are spun up for three hours, prior to activating d03. Three domains are then spun up for an additional six hours period before starting d04. All four domains are spun up for another 50 min. Next, the finest resolution LES domain, d05, including the WLG model, is activated to allow the development of fine-scale

Figure 4: Comparison of the vertical profiles of 1-hour average horizontal wind speed, \bar{U} (first row), wind direction, $\bar{\beta}$ (second row), and potential temperature, $\bar{\theta}$ (third row), obtained from TSE04 (first column), TSE09 (second column) and TSE13 (third column), and WLG model. Black and red horizontal lines indicate the standard deviation around the mean value obtained during the averaging period of the measurement data and simulation results, respectively (a.g.l refers to above ground level).

turbulent structures within the atmospheric boundary layer. The final restart run, which is the actual run discussed herein, takes 70 min (corresponding to the time window between 21:50-23:00 UTC on 09/05/2017). The first 10 minutes of the final restart run are discarded to allow the turbulent flow field to be thoroughly mixed across d05, prior to running the actual simulation for the corresponding time frame.

2.3. Wind turbine wake modeling using the WRF-LES-GAL model

The wind turbine operating in the test field is an Enercon E-82 2MW. Unfortunately, the design data required for proper GAL-based modeling is unavailable. Hence, a publicly available design database of a similar wind turbine, the generic Vestas V80 2MW machine [18], is used. The Enercon WT has 80 m hub height and 82 m rotor diameter, whereas the Vestas wind turbine has 78 m hub height and 80 m rotor diameter. Nacelle and tower effects are parameterized utilizing an approach similar to that of the WLG model. The rotor speed is regulated using a speed

Figure 5: Spectra of velocity components (a-i) and potential temperature (j-l) during 1-hour period, plotted as a function of non-dimensional frequency normalized by hub height, H , and 1-hour average horizontal freestream wind speed at hub height, \bar{U} . “ma” refers to the moving average data from the WLG model and met masts, consisting of an averaging interval of 25 data points.

controller algorithm and a simple pitch controller is utilized to control the blade pitch angle. Minor differences between the two wind turbines are not expected to significantly affect this study because the mean wind speed considered during the period of interest is below the rated speed of the modeled WT, and for those wind speeds, the C_T curves for both wind turbines are very similar. The stationary curves of power, thrust, power and thrust coefficients, versus wind speed are presented in Figure 1 for both wind turbines.

3. Results

3.1. Time series and vertical profiles

Figure 2 shows the terrain elevation and layout over the Perdigão with the locations of the wind turbine, met masts and lidars at the test site. Wake and offset transects, indicated by dotted and dashed black lines, respectively, are used to analyze the wind flow field in vertical planes, whereas time series and vertical profiles of horizontal wind speed, wind direction and potential temperature gradient are obtained from 100 m DTU met masts (TSE04, TSE09 and TSE13) and are used as reference to validate the WLG results. Figure 2b illustrates 1-hour average horizontal wind speed color map at hub height, during the 1-hour period analyzed.

Due to slight misalignment between the mean wind direction and wake transect ($\sim 6^\circ$), the wind turbine wake was not precisely aligned with DLR lidars scanning vertical planes. Although this minor difference has a negligible effect on the near wake behavior of the wind turbine below hub height ($0.5D-1D$, with D being the rotor diameter), it precludes the exact comparison of the wake velocity deficit profiles reproduced by the model along the wake transect with those obtained from lidar scans. In order to improve the comparison between the simulated

Figure 6: Cospectra of the u - and v -velocity components (a-c), vertical turbulent stresses, i.e., u - and w - (d-f) and v - and w - (g-i) velocity components and cospectra of the w -velocity component and potential temperature (j-l) that are normalized by corresponding covariances during 1-hour period, plotted as a function of non-dimensional frequency normalized by hub height, H , and horizontal wind speed at freestream at hub height, \bar{U} . Note that only absolute values of the cospectra are shown. “ma” refers to the moving average data from the WLG model and met masts, consisting of an averaging interval of 25 data points.

wake velocity field and the experimental lidar data, the longitudinal, u , and lateral, v , velocity components are projected onto a rotated coordinate system aligned with the wake transect.

Figure 3 presents time series of horizontal wind speed and wind direction at hub height and 100-10 m potential temperature gradient from three different DTU met masts and WRF-LES for the 1-hour period analyzed herein. The sampling frequency of the experimental data is 20 Hz, whereas the WRF-LES outputs are recorded every time step during 1-hour simulation period, corresponding to a sampling frequency of about 133 Hz; therefore, the numerical data were subsampled to 0.05 s intervals to match the experimental data. Simulated horizontal wind speeds at hub height are overestimated compared to measurements taken from met masts. Also, WRF-LES predicts the wind direction at the ridges (TSE04 and TSE13) reasonably well, yet large variations are observed in the valley (TSE09), most probably due to the difficulties to capture the larger turbulence mixing exhibited by the model in this region. Positive potential temperature gradients close to zero are observed in the model results, meaning that near-neutral-stable conditions are modeled during the period of interest. Experimental data from all met masts indicate a transitional regime between unstable and stable ABL conditions across the ridges.

The 1-hour mean vertical profiles of the various variables with their respective standard deviations over the period of interest are presented in Figure 4. The overprediction of wind speed exhibited by WRF-LES at the ridges is likely due to the overestimated flow acceleration on the slopes. Nevertheless, the numerical results agree well with the TSE09 met mast data

Figure 7: Comparison of instantaneous horizontal wind velocity snapshots along the wake transect from DLR85 lidar and WLG model at approximately 22:41 UTC (top) and from DLR86 lidar and WLG model at approximately 22:27 UTC (bottom). The wind turbine is represented schematically by the black solid line.

below hub height. WRF-LES model predicts the wind direction reasonably well at different heights on the ridges. This is expected because the predominant wind direction in the test field is approximately perpendicular to the orientation of the ridges, according to the annual climatology at Perdigoão [3]. However, it is largely biased in the valley due, most probably, to the difficulties of the WRF-LES model in reproducing the enhanced turbulent mixing levels at that particular location. The vertical profiles of the 1-hour average potential temperature predicted by the numerical model do not vary significantly at the met mast locations.

3.2. Turbulence spectra

Figure 5 shows power spectra of longitudinal (a-c), lateral (d-f) and vertical (g-i) velocity components, as well as potential temperature (j-l) obtained at hub height at the met mast locations. A first-order low-pass Butterworth filter is applied to remove the aliasing effect, which appears approximately after $fH/\bar{U} = 10$, in the potential temperature spectra ((j-l) in Figure 5) and cospectra of the vertical velocity and potential temperature ((j-l) in Figure 6). Values from experimental and numerical data are computed using the Welch method and by dividing 1-hour time series into 20-min windows (10-min overlapping intervals using Hann window). A moving average algorithm, consisting of an averaging interval of 25 data points, is applied to obtain a smoother representation of the spectra and cospectra. The power spectra of the three velocity components are in good agreement with the measured spectra (a-i), except for the sudden energy drop in the low-to-mid frequency range from TSE04 met mast. The spectra from WRF-LES model attenuate faster at higher-frequency due to low-pass filtering and numerics involved in the model.

Spectra of potential temperature are overestimated in the mid-to-high frequency range by the WLG model for all met masts. This may be attributed to the improper set-up of the CPM parameters prior to the simulation. Muñoz-Esparza *et al.* [34] proposed a perturbation time scale, Γ , which considers the relative time taken by the flow to be advected across a cell being perturbed. They suggest $\Gamma \approx 1$, in order not to miss perturbations for a long time ($\Gamma \gg 1$) or rapidly impose new perturbations ($\Gamma \ll 1$). In this work, $\Gamma = 1$ is used.

Figure 8: Comparison of 1-hour average horizontal wind velocity from DLR85 (top left), DLR86 (top right), DTU (bottom left) lidars and WLG model (bottom right). Note that the color map of DTU lidars is plotted along the offset transect, whereas others are cross-sections along the wake transect (see Figure 2 for details). The wind turbine is represented schematically by the solid black line.

Figure 6 illustrates the uv (a-c), uw (d-f), vw (g-i) and $w\theta$ (j-l) cospectra, respectively. Cospectra of different simulated velocity components agree fairly well with the measurement data from all DTU towers. Sensible heat flux cospectrum from the WLG model reveals a higher energy content in the low-to-mid frequency range compared to the measured cospectrum from TSE04 and lower energy content up to roughly 0.04 Hz than the measured cospectrum from TSE09, respectively. Simulated and measured cospectra from TSE13 are in good agreement, despite a discrepancy observed in the mid-to-high frequency range.

3.3. Wind turbine wake velocity fields and aerodynamic performance

Snapshots of instantaneous along-transect velocity fields from DLR lidars and WLG model are shown in Figure 7. Although the data from the lidar scans were postprocessed, additional filtering was applied by eliminating velocity values with carrier-to-noise ratios less than -24 dB.

Snapshots from DLR85 and WLG, presented in the first row of the figure, are taken at approximately 22:41 UTC, whereas snapshots from DLR86 and the numerical model are taken at approximately 22:27 UTC. Transitions of unsteady turbulent flow structures are challenging to capture due to large variability in the modeled and observed wind fields. Therefore, comparisons of instantaneous snapshots of wind fields from the model and observations will likely not match, especially in a complex terrain where wind flow is highly three-dimensional. However, the comparison of instantaneous snapshots of the flow fields along the wake and offset transects may provide additional information about the wake formation, as well as recirculation zones occurring downstream of the wind turbine into the valley at a particular time instant.

Figure 8 illustrates the 1-hour average horizontal wind velocity from DLR and DTU lidars and WLG. Both DLR85 and DLR86 lidars capture the upward deflection of the wake, which extends up to ~ 200 m downstream of the wind turbine. The WLG model predicts the horizontal extension of the wake quite well, but it does not indicate the upward shift of the wake centerline observed in DLR lidar scans. This is probably due to the underestimation of the impact of buoyant forces (i.e., vertical kinematic heat flux, $\overline{w'\theta'}$) that affects upward-downward turbulence

Figure 9: (a) Locations of the corresponding wake velocity deficit (VD) profiles shown below, as a function of non-dimensional height, with H and D being the hub height and rotor diameter, respectively. Dashed black line indicates the inflow location, whereas the black dotted lines represent different leeward locations from the mountain top into the valley (a). 1-hour average wake velocity deficit profiles obtained from WLG simulation and DLR lidars at different downstream locations of the wind turbine (b). Red horizontal lines, and blue and yellow shaded regions cover the mean \pm standard deviations of velocity deficits during the 1-hour averaging period of the simulation results and measurement data, respectively.

mixing in the model (see the temperature gradient in Figure 3). A recirculation zone (observed in the 1-hour average horizontal velocity field) is formed in the lee side of the first ridge, which is captured by all lidars. DTU lidar scans (bottom left plot in Figure 8) provide information about the wind flow topology undisturbed by the wind turbine wake along the offset transect parallel to the wake transect. Although the WLG model is able to model the recirculating flow, from the lee side of the first ridge into the valley, during the simulation period, the magnitude of the wind velocity in the recirculation zone is underestimated compared to the remote sensing data. The 1-hour bias in mean horizontal wind velocity above ~ 600 m is on the order of 6 m s^{-1} . Figure 9 shows the locations and corresponding velocity deficit profiles from DLR lidars and the results from the WLG model. In order to obtain such vertical profiles, lidar data were interpolated to the model's wake transect plane. The dashed black line denotes the velocity deficit profile at $1D$ upstream of the wind turbine. Wake velocity deficit (VD) profiles that are plotted as a function

Figure 10: Time series of power, P , thrust, T , rotational speed, Ω , and pitch angle, θ_p , of the generic Vestas V80 wind turbine modeled by WLG. Dashed black line denotes the mean value.

of non-dimensional height, $(z - H)/D$, are obtained as

$$VD(z) = \frac{\overline{U}_\infty(z) - \overline{U}(z)}{\overline{U}_{hub}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\overline{U}_\infty(z)$ is the horizontal wind speed profile at upstream, $\overline{U}(z)$ is the 1-hour average wind speed profile at different downstream locations and \overline{U}_{hub} is the mean horizontal wind speed at freestream at hub height. VD s from lidars and the model cannot be compared directly, as there is an upward drift (~ 20 m at $x/D = 0.5$) in the modeled wake. However, a similar flow deceleration in wake velocity is observed both in the experiments and in the results from the numerical model, up to $1D$, but the modeled wake stretches further downstream. The modeled far-wake VD s match reasonably well and stay in the region covering the mean \pm standard deviations of VD , although the 1-hour average VD profiles are slightly different. Nacelle and tower have no significant impact in both the modeled and observed wake velocity deficit profiles.

Figure 10 displays time series of wind turbine rotor and generator power, thrust, rotational speed and pitch angle over the simulated 1-hour period. The current WLG model uses a five-region speed controller algorithm in order to regulate the rotor speed [35]. Furthermore, a simple pitch controller mechanism is used to control the blade pitch angle at speeds above rated wind speed. The pitch controller was active only for a limited time when the inflow wind speed seen by the rotor at $1D$ upstream exceeded the rated rotor speed. The 1-hour average aerodynamic power is about 1313 kW, the generator power is 1222 kW, the rotor speed is 18.4 RPM, and the blade pitch angle is about -0.48° . Compared to the power and thrust curves of the generic Vestas V80 given by Churchfield *et al.* [18] in Figure 1, a positive bias of about 0.08 in the thrust coefficient, C_t , 0.16 in the aerodynamic power coefficient, C_{pr} , and 0.15 in the generator power coefficient, C_{pg} at an average wind speed of 9 m s^{-1} is observed.

4. Conclusions

A simulation of an isolated wind turbine operating on top of the SW ridge of Perdigão Valley has been performed using a combination of the Weather Research and Forecasting-Large Eddy

Simulation-Generalized Actuator Line models (WRF-LES-GAL or WLG). The simulated flow field results have been compared with existing experimental data from the Perdigão experimental campaign. Numerical results from the met masts have shown that the time series and vertical profiles of horizontal wind speed, wind direction and potential temperature agree reasonably well with experimental data, despite the minor differences in the vertical profiles of horizontal wind speed on the ridges and wind direction in the valley. Overall, the WLG model overestimates the 1-hour average horizontal wind speed at hub height about 2.71, 1.32 and 4.85 m s⁻¹ over the first ridge (TSE04), in the valley (TSE09) and over the second ridge (TSE13), respectively. The 1-hour average bias between WRF-LES and measurements of wind direction at hub height is -8.69° at the first ridge, 82.34° in the valley and 8° at the second ridge, respectively. For temperature gradient, the 1-hour average bias error is less than 0.02 K m⁻¹, yet it is positive at TSE04 and negative at TSE09, while it is -0.006 K m⁻¹ at the second ridge. The simulated wake is not entirely aligned with the vertical scan planes of the DLR lidars. Besides, the wake is deflected after a few rotor diameters downstream, towards the north of the DLR lidars (see the ideal wake transect and modeled wake encircled in black in Figure 2), making the comparison of modeled wake behavior with lidar data difficult. Insufficient buoyancy generation is likely responsible for the discrepancy between modeled and observed wake results. Apart from that, wind turbine's aerodynamic behavior agrees fairly well with the power and thrust data given in Figure 1. Spectra and cospectra of various quantities show that the current WLG setup is a promising approach to capture transient turbulent flow structures as well as microscale flow features that are important in wake modeling, despite the shortcomings explained previously. Further studies should also explore the effect of different physical parameterizations and the CPM parameters to have a best-practice case set-up prior to analyzing the period of interest.

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